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**DETERMINATION OF THE FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PASSAGE OF
CERVITIS AND NON-SPECIFIC VAGINITIS AND ITS RECURRENCE***Matqurbonova Sh.B.¹, Ismoilova D.O'.²**¹Master of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Urganch Branch, Tashkent Medical Academy
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Purpose: *Determination of the main factors affecting the course of cervicitis and nonspecific vaginitis, its recurrence.*

Key words: *cervicitis, recurrence, vaginitis, microflora, ultrasonic cavitation, infection, antibiotic.*

Relevance: Inflammatory diseases of the vagina and cervix - vaginitis and cervicitis - the most common health problems of women, sometimes become chronic due to lack of timely treatment and often recur. lowers the quality of sexual and social life and can lead to other serious complications (infertility, intrauterine infection of the fetus, inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs, chronic pain in the pelvic area, postpartum complications, etc.). Infectious and inflammatory diseases of the lower part of the genital tract occupy a leading place in gynecological pathology. At the same time, among vaginal infections, nonspecific vaginitis is more common than that caused by specific pathogens, reaching 76-80%. In postmenopausal women, vaginitis and cervicitis occur due to the activation of conditionally pathogenic microorganisms against the background of a low level of sex hormones and a decrease in the number of lactobacilli.

Inflammation is caused by specific infections (gonococcus, trichomanade, genital mycoplasma, chlamydia) and some diseases, conditionally pathogenic microorganisms (E. coli, staphylococci, streptococci, gardnerella, candida) against the background of decreased immunity.

Recurrent nonspecific vaginitis causes a number of complications: infertility, menstrual disorders, adhesion disease, the risk of increasing the oncogenic potential of viruses, infection of the upper parts of the genital tract, and can cause morphological changes in the cervix.

It has been shown that non-specific conditionally pathogenic flora can play an important role in the emergence of chronic exo- and endocervicitis.

According to many studies, infection is a factor in the failure of self-sustaining reparative regeneration of the organ, and in 3.6-9.0% of cases, the uterine cavity, where the cylindrical and

metaplastic epithelium is most sensitive to infectious agents. It makes it possible for cancer to appear in the same ectopic zone.

Studies in this direction have shown that the inflammatory process is interrelated with a decrease in local immunity, disruption of blood supply in the stroma and regeneration of cells of the epithelial layer, and this process leads to relapse, i.e. prolongation of its chronicity. contributes. At the same time, the inflammatory process of the cervix is rarely isolated and is often combined with various pathological processes (ectopy, polyps, hyperkeratosis, dysplasia, etc.), which leads to tragic consequences.

The risk factors that contribute to the chronicity of the process can be divided into the following groups:

- mechanical - intrauterine device (especially long-term use);
- hard synthetic clothing, non-observance of hygienic conditions, hot climate;
- endocrine - occurs with diabetes, pathology of the thyroid gland and its hypofunction;
- iatrogenic - long-term and uncontrolled use of antibiotics, taking corticosteroids, immunosuppressants, oral contraceptives.

The increased interest of European and American doctors in the study of cervicitis and vaginitis is associated with a significant increase in the frequency of the disease in recent years. This is due to a sharp increase in the number of risk factors for the development of diseases, as well as environmental changes. One of the main reasons for this is the deterioration of the environmental situation, poor nutrition, frequent stress, uncontrolled use of drugs - primarily antibacterial drugs and hormonal contraceptives.

Material and methods. 50 women of reproductive age who applied with the diagnosis of cervicitis and nonspecific vaginitis were examined.

In female patients:

- Anamnesis (complaints, illness, vites);
- clinical examination;
- laboratory (general and biochemical blood analysis, cultural analysis of vaginal smear);

Results and analyses: During 1 month, 50 women applied with cervicitis and nonspecific vaginitis. Analyzing the obtained results, it was found in Figure 1 that 64% of women have symptoms and 36% have no symptoms. In Figure 2, among the main factors that cause recurrence of the disease in female patients, 44% of women take the first place due to excessive and frequent use of antibiotics, followed by menstruation in 24%, sexual organs in 22%. non-observance of hygiene and 10% caused by extragenital diseases.

Summary: The disease was mainly characterized by a symptomatic course. The main reason for relapses (44% of female patients) was associated with taking too many antibiotics.

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